

EDU TRACKS

February 2014

A Monthly Scanner of Trends in Education

Vol. 13 No. 6

**DIAGNOSIS IN
MATH CURRICULUM**

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MONITORING QUALITY**

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MEETING THE CHALLENGES**

**SCHOOL STUDENTS
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Printed & Published by

Suresh Chandra Sharma

Managing Director,

Neelkamal Publications Pvt. Ltd.,

on behalf of

Neelkamal Publications Pvt. Ltd.,

Koti, Hyderabad - 500 095, India.

☎ : 91-40-24757140, 91-40-24757197,

Fax : 91-40-24757951.

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Delhi Office: BG5/9B, Paschim Vihar,

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☎ : 91-11-25285894

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Computer-Assisted Instruction and Audio Program

Which One is More Effective?

Research

Computer has become the basic requirement of the present education system and schools have also started using computers for its effectiveness. The computer assisted instruction is being used in the teaching-learning process. There is another technique of teaching called as Audio programme in which the students learn through hearing. In the present study the investigators have conducted an experimental research and compared the effectiveness of both the methods and found the most suitable technique for the present generation learners.

CAI is defined as the use of computer to provide course content instruction in the form of drill and practice, tutorials and simulation.

– Chambers & Sprecher (1983)

The present education system of India is concentrating much on the pedagogy. The pedagogical strategies are the backbone of teaching-learning process. Sharma (2008 p. 62) defines a good teaching as having a provision of learning experiences so that the teaching objectives may be achieved as a result of desired modifications in the behaviour of pupils. For the enhancement of teaching effectiveness the educational technology can play an important role. The definition of Educational technology by Kumar (2009, p. 4) is a complex, integrated process involving people, procedures, ideas, devices, and organization, for analysing problems and devising, implementing, evaluating, and managing solutions to those problems, involved in all aspects of human learning. The educational technology has contributed many teaching techniques like microteaching, simulation, models of teaching and also use of AV-aids audio programme, video programme and CAI etc.

The present day learners are more logistic and they have easy access to the information of new technologies through media. In this context, the teachers have to make use of ICT and other new techniques in teaching learning process. To imbibe these new techniques the teachers must be aware of the best and most suitable option. Therefore, in the present research study the investigators have tried to find the most suitable technique by comparing audio

programmes and CAI programmes. The investigation study, is an experimental study which compares the academic achievement of the students by teaching with two different methods namely audio programme and CAI programme.

Audio teaching is nothing but providing content-based instruction through audio media. The students have to hear the lessons and understand it and this requires a listening comprehension and creative imagination. This concept is not a new one, already many radio programmes are going on in which the lessons are being taught through Radio. In the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) scheme listening of radio lesson is made compulsory to the primary students. Teaching aids/equipments which are used in audio teaching are known as audio aids. Audio aids mean those sources in which only hearing organs are used i.e., knowledge is gained mainly through the ears. Audio educational programmes have, therefore immense partialities. Particularly in developing countries like India, where constraints of finance, efficient teachers, suitable equipment and appliances adversely affect educational planning administration, audio programmes play a significant part in expansion as well as qualitative improvement of education. (Patel, 2008 pg. no. 24)

Mohanty (2007 p. 288) defines CAI is an interesting innovation technique of educational technology. It has better flexibility and more versatility than any of the teaching machine. It can cater information to the student and test their learning and then give immediate feedback. Therefore, it can be used as a supplementary strategy to classroom teaching learning process. Repetition of this process can make the students

perfect their understanding of the content. The time taken by the student and extent of correctness of the student can be stored by the computer and this will help the teachers to provide the relevant materials. This is the best technique for individual learning, because in CAI the student is evaluated who gives his/her performance record and then the teacher can guide the students in his/her areas and CAI also helps the students to learn till he becomes master in the respective content area. CAI works on the Programmed learning method. In the words of J. D. Williams: "Programmed learning may be defined as the arrangement of material to be learned into an orderly series of learning experiences, in each of which material is presented to the learner, a response as elicited and feedback given". (Aggarwal & Gupta, 2010, pg. no. 70) In CAI each student sits in front of computer screen which displays information. A complete learning package suiting to individual need is presented sequentially. This package may consist of video as well as audio tape recordings, films, slides, film strips and so on the student may make queries to the computer by means of a typewriter keyboard and get answer in printed forms. On completion of a programme, the computer records his progress and prints out a report for the teacher.

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Objectives

- To prepare the audio and CAI programme in science subject for 10th standard.
- To impart the lesson through audio and CAI programme.
- To compare the effectiveness of teaching between audio and CAI programme.

Hypotheses

- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for pre test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for post test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for pre test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for post test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through CAI programme for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.
- ◆ There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through CAI for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.

Review of Related Literature

The literature available from encyclopaedia, reference books, journals, surveys of educational researches, Internet and other research sources were

referred for in-depth knowledge about the intended problem.

- Patel (2008) found that the Nodi-Keli-kali audio-visual package developed for the study was effective and helpful to the students of both III and IV standard in learning the EVS.
- Dhamija (1985) found that radio programme when mixed with certain visuals become effective.
- Phalachandra (2003) found that the content based Keli-Kali radio broadcast in audio format was useful at primary stage. He also found that the students of radio schools have achieved better. They attended school regularly. The scheduled caste/ tribe children achievement was worth mentioning. These programmes have made the teachers understand the objectives, content and they covered all the topics as described in the Keli-Kali handbook. These programmes have enhanced the inter-school curricular competitions.
- Basturk (2005) findings suggest participants' learning capacity of the introductory statistics could be improved successfully when CAI used as a supplement to regular lecture in teaching introductory statistics course.
- Rabia (2004), the data of her study revealed that the students taught through computer-assisted instruction as supplementary strategy performed significantly better. The students with high achievement level showed better results than those with low achievement level when taught through computer-assisted instruction. The computer-assisted instruction was found equally effective for both male and female students.
- The study of Wade (2001) indicated that computer assisted instruction is an effective method of delivering information literacy skills instruction. Students were able to select an appropriate database for their topic and navigate through, select, and print information that supported their focus questions with minimal involvement on the part of the teacher. The tutorial/practice

model proved to be effective. This model more thoroughly integrated information literacy skills into the curriculum and solved the logistical problems of media specialists teaching all students.

Methodology

The investigators designed an experimental study with a group of students having homogeneity based on intelligence score as measured on standard progressive matrices (SPM) of Raven's test. Different types of teaching or treatment was provided to the sample which was assigned randomly to two different groups. The effectiveness of role of audio and CAI programme was tested through comparison of scores obtained on pre and post test. The details of study are given in following paragraphs.

Sampling

The purposive random sampling method was adopted for finalising sample. Before finalising the sample population, the investigators conducted SPM test on the whole class. The students whose scores on this test were falling on average category were selected; each group consisted of 30 students and was randomly assigned to experimental-1 and experimental-2 group respectively. Thus, the equivalent groups were selected for the study.

Variables of the Study

Control Variable: The intelligence of the students.

Independent Variable: The methods of teaching namely audio and CAI programme.

Dependent Variable: The academic achievement of the students

Tools of the Study

- *SPM test:* The Standard Progressive Matrices test developed by Raven was conducted on the students to know their intelligence.
- *Science textbook:* The tenth standard science text book of Karnataka state was selected as the basis for Science content. Solar energy unit was identified from the text book. For teaching after finding its sustainability for both the methods.
- *Audio programme:* The content based audio programmes of 30 minutes

duration were developed for the teaching students of 10th standard.

➤ *CAI programme:* The content based CAI programmes were developed for teaching students of 10th standard which could generally be completed by studies in 30 minutes.

➤ *Achievement test:* Teacher made achievement test for pre and post test for both the units of teaching were prepared for testing the student's performance before and after the experimental treatment.

Treatments for Study

The students were taught with two different methods of teaching viz., audio and CAI programme. The procedure of development and other related details are given below:

Development of Audio Programme

This is an important aspect of present research. The first stage in development of audio programme was planning. In this stage the investigators prepared work schedule and selected the content for the programme besides planning for the development of entire tool. This was followed by script writing, and before writing the script the investigators prepared the guidelines of audio script writing and wrote the audio script. The script was corrected by investigators for which they consulted with eminent research scholars, experts and educationist for content aspects. The final script was discussed with the media expert and converted it into audio recording script. In the next stage the investigators identified the characters and their voice testing was done. The script was given to most suitable voice characters. This was the most important step when the characters rehearsed their role. An audio studio was set in which all the characters were seated comfortably. First the voice of all the characters was tested to set microphones for recording and then they read the whole script according to their role in conversational format. At editing stage all the mistakes were corrected. The pauses or instances of confusion were removed, the repetitions of the words were cut and the other sound defects were also corrected and finally the error free audio programme was ready. The programmes, thus developed were subjected to tryout in schools and feedback was obtained from students and teachers. This feedback was incorporated in final editing and ultimately programmes were thus made error free.

Development of CAI Package

The development of CAI package is a long process and is also an important aspect of present research. Hence, the investigators gave due importance for development of CAI packages. In CAI the computer provides text and multiple choice questions or problems to students, gives an immediate response to the answers given, summarizes students' performance, and generates exercises for worksheets and tests. (Siddiqui, 2009) Considering this format the stages involved in the development and standardisation of package are given below.

The programme planning was the first stage, where in the investigators decided about the content, format of preparation of package, style of teaching, physical and financial requirements etc. This was carried forward with design of a CAI programme based on requirements of the stakeholders. The CAI has four style of presentation and the investigators

restricted for use of tutorial and drill & practice modes of teaching at secondary school level children in this study. The investigators then referred the material and planned outline of script and wrote the academic script of CAI programme. This was followed by consultations with software experts, who helped in finalisation of CAI script based on media requirements. The programmers or software experts were then asked to prepare CAI packages. At this stage the content and context specific pictures, animations, questions and feedbacks were integrated properly. Care was taken that the objectives of the programme remained prime concern. The media and content experts reviewed the programmes, edited and incorporated important aspects at appropriate places. The programme, thus developed was subjected to try-out in schools. The programmes were tested for their effectiveness with regard to software, type or format of CAI and planning aspects. The errors free programmes were sent for final implementation in the schools. Based on defects the programmes correction at appropriate stages were incorporated till quality programme was prepared.

Statistical Techniques

The investigators used statistical techniques like Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value for testing the hypothesis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

H1: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for pre test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 1,

Table-1: Showing t-value between Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 Group for Pre test-1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	4.63	0.98	0.28	1.60*
Exptl2	30	29	4.17	1.28		

* not significant

From table 1, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 1.60 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.76. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H1 is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the Means of experimental-1 and experimental-2 group for pre test score for the unit solar energy 1.

H2: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for post test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 2,

Table-2: Showing t-value between Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group for Post test 1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	13.8	0.92	0.28	35.97*
Exptl2	30	29	23.17	1.12		

* significant

From table 2, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 35.97 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.76. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H2 is rejected. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between the Means of experimental-1 and experimental-2 group on post test score on solar energy1. After observing the Means of both the groups it can be drawn that the Mean score is in favour of experimental-2. That is after treatment the achievement of experimental-2 group is better than experimental-1group.

H3: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for pre test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 3,

Table-3: Showing t-value between Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group for Pre test 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	4.23	1.04	0.27	0*
Exptl2	30	29	4.23	1.07		

* not significant

From table 3, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 0 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.76. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H3 is accepted. Hence, it indicates that there is no significant difference between the means of experimental-1 and experimental-2 group.

H4: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme and the students taught through CAI programme for post test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 4,

Table-4: Showing t-value between Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 Group for Post test 2 in the Unit Solar Energy 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	13.73	1.11	0.28	22.85*
Exptl2	30	29	20.33	1.12		

* Significant

The table 4 indicates that the calculated value of 't' is 22.85 and the table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H4 is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between means of experimental-1 and experimental-2 group for post test 2 of solar energy 2. Looking at the means it can be inferred that the mean score is in favour of experimental-2 group. That means after treatment the achievement of experimental-2 group is better than experimental-1group.

H5: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 5,

Table-5: Showing t-value between Pre test and Post test of Experimental-1Group for Solar Energy-1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.63	0.98	0.25	37.10*
Post test	30	29	13.8	0.92		

* Significant

From table 5, value at 0.01 level is 2.76 and the calculated value is 37.10, which is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre test and post test scores of experimental-1group in solar energy 1. The Means of both the scores indicates that experimental-1group students perform well after teaching.

H6: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through audio programme for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 6,

Table-6: Showing t-value between Pre test and Post test of Experimental-1Group for Solar Energy2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.23	1.04	0.28	34.17*
Post test	30	29	13.73	1.11		

* Significant

From table 6, value at 0.01 level is 2.76 and the calculated value is 34.17, which is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between means of pre test and post test of experimental-1group in solar energy 2 unit. The Means of both the scores indicates that experimental-1group students perform very well after teaching unit solar energy 2.

H7: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through CAI programme for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 7,

Table-7: Showing t-value between Pre test and Post test of Experimental-2 Group for Solar Energy1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.17	1.28	0.31	61.02*
Post test	30	29	23.17	1.12		

* Significant

From table 7, value at 0.01 level is 2.76 and the calculated value is 61.02, which is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre test and post test of experimental-2 group for solar energy 1 unit. The Means

of both the scores indicates that experimental-2 group students performed very well after treatment or teaching through audio visual programme.

H8: There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught through CAI for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 8,

Table-8: Showing t-value between Pre test and Post test of Experimental-2 Group for Solar Energy-2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.23	1.07	0.28	56.65*
Post test	30	29	20.33	1.12		

* Significant

From table 8, value at 0.01 level is 2.76 and the calculated value is 56.65, which is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre test and post test of experimental-2 group for solar energy 2 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that experimental-2 group students performed very well after treatment or teaching through audio visual programme.

Major Findings

- Both the groups under study, which were taught through audio and CAI programmes possessed no difference with regard to their pre test scores on the unit on solar energy-1 or possessed uniform knowledge about the unit before teaching.
- The group which was taught unit solar energy-1 through CAI programme achieved more than that of the group taught by audio programme.
- Both the groups under study, which were taught through audio and CAI programmes possessed no difference with regard to their pre test scores on the unit on solar energy-2 or possessed uniform knowledge about the unit before teaching.
- The group which was taught unit solar energy-2 through CAI programme achieved more than that of the group taught by audio programme.
- The group which was taught unit solar energy-1 through audio programme achieved more after treatment.
- The group which was taught unit solar energy-2 through audio programme achieved more after treatment.
- The group which was taught unit solar energy-1 through CAI programme achieved more after treatment.
- The group which was taught unit solar energy-2 through CAI programme achieved more after treatment.

Conclusion

The present study shows the use of audio and CAI programme in teaching

learning process. The student taught by CAI programme achieved much better than the students taught through audio programme. Therefore the education system must use the CAI programme as a supplementary strategy for teaching learning process. The CAI programme is innovative and attractive for the students of our country. With proper teacher support system CAI programme can be introduced in the Indian classrooms for better and advanced learning for our students.

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